

On the Composition and Stability of Beryllium and Thorium Complexes of Solochrome Azurine B. S.

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Solochrome dyes were known to the chemists long back but only recently they have found an extensive use as analytical reagents¹⁻⁴. Tandon and coworkers for the first time used solochrome azurine B.S. with the following formula, for the micro-detection of copper and thorium^{5,6}. Beside these nothing notable has so far been done on the reaction of this dye with metals. The present communication deals with the composition and stability of solochrome azurine B.S. complexes of Be(II) and Th(IV). Preliminary experiments have shown that these metals react with this dye to give a deep violet coloured complex in acetate buffer of pH 4.0 to 5.5.

Thorium nitrate, beryllium sulphate, sodium acetate and acetic acid were all A.R. grade (B.D.H.) reagents. Solochrome azurine B.S. (S.A.B.S.) was supplied by I.C.I., India Ltd. The stock solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water and diluted to the desired strength with acetate buffer. A freshly prepared solution of the dye was used since there was some tendency of sedimentation on standing.

Instruments, the experimental setup and the procedure are the same as in my previous communication⁷.

Application of the method of Vosburgh and Cooper⁸ to the systems Be(II)-S.A.B.S. and Th(IV)-S.A.B.S. (in the ratio 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 2 : 1 M to L) keeping total volume 20.0 ml. and pH 5.0 demonstrates the formation of one complex in each case having λ_{max}

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at $560\text{ m}\mu$ and $600\text{ m}\mu$ respectively. The reactants have negligible absorbance at the chosen wavelengths. The composition of the interaction product was determined by applying Job's method of continuous variation⁹ and the molar ratio method¹⁰. For Job's method,

FIG. 1 - JOB'S METHOD

equimolar solutions of metal and S.A.B.S. of concentration $0.0002M$ and $0.00013M$ were mixed according to the method of continuous variation. The curves for the reaction of BeSO₄ and dye are shown in Fig. 1. Similar curves were obtained for thorium. The stability constants of the complexes were calculated from the data given by Job's method,

FIG. 2 - AMPEROMETRIC TITRATIONS

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Amperometric titrations were carried out at -1.25V . The composition of the complexes was found to be in the ratio 1 : 1 by spectrophotometric methods. The results were supported by amperometric titrations (Fig. 2). The values of stability constants are 0.5×10^5 and 0.25×10^6 for beryllium and thorium complexes respectively.

On shaking the aqueous solution of the complex with carbon tetrachloride, the dye transferred to the organic layer with a violet coloured product floating at the junction. Work is in progress on the studies of the solid complexes.

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